

B1503

Post-mortem analysis from barrier layer's large-area cells made by PLD aged for 14,000 h in SOFC mode

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Abstract

Gadolinium-doped ceria (CGO) barrier layer placed between yttrium-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) electrolyte and strontium-based electrode aims to avoid the formation of insulating phase SrZrO_3 during solid oxide fuel cell operation. However, this phase was observed in as-fabricated state-of-the-art cells, which evidences cation inter-diffusion during the sintering process [1]. The use of vacuum techniques such as sputtering and Large Area Pulsed Laser Deposition (LA-PLD) allows the implementation of dense layers at lower temperature compared with traditional deposition techniques (i. e. screen printing). CGO barrier layer deposition and annealing parameters were optimized in a previous work from the group and led to an increase of 70% in power density at 750°C and 0.7 V compared to a state-of-the-art button cell. Remarkable results were also obtained when the PLD barrier layer was up-scaled to large area cells of 80 cm² and tested in short-stack configuration for long-term operation [2].

This short-stack, that includes state-of-the-art cells as well as the large-area PLD ones, was aged for a total of 14,000 h at 750°C for the first 8,000 h and 700°C until the end of the experiment. Cells with PLD barrier layer showed enhanced initial performances with a low degradation rate.

This work presents a post-mortem characterization of the barrier layers and interfaces in both types of cells. Scanning-electronic microscope, Electron Probe Micro Analysis with Wavelength Dispersive X-Ray (EPMA-WDX) and micro-Raman spectroscopy were used to observe any microstructural changes as well as any changes in composition due to cation inter-diffusion.

[1] Morales et al., Journal of Power Sources 344 (2017) 141-151.

[2] Morales et al. ACS Applied Energy Materials 1 (2018) 1955-1964.

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Introduction

Many SOFCs are now using the mixed ionic–electronic conductor $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Co}_{1-y}\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_3$ (LSCF) as material for the cathode in order to get higher performance and to avoid typical problems of delamination when using $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{MoO}_3$ (LSM) [1]. However, insulating phases such as strontium zirconate (SrZrO_3) and lanthanum zirconate ($\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$) are formed when LSCF is in contact with state-of-the-art (SoA) yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) electrolyte [2]. Secondary phases with low conductivity like Co_3O_4 , $\text{Co}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, or $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4-x}\text{FeO}_3$ can also be favoured at regions where Sr diffused and got expelled from the LSCF structure [3,4]. To avoid the diffusion of Sr and Zr from the cathode and the electrolyte, respectively, and so the formation of insulating phases, a barrier layer made of CeO_2 doped with Gd, Sm or Y is placed between the two layers [5]. SoA barrier layers are usually made by screen-printing and densified at high sintering temperatures ($\geq 1,200$ °C), which consequently activates inter-diffusion processes between ceria and YSZ and leads to the formation of solid solutions, dopant migration and even Kirkendall voids [6,7].

Alternative deposition techniques to avoid reaching such high temperatures are vacuum deposition methods able to fabricate dense and thin layers between room temperature and 1,000 °C [8-12]. Especially, pulsed laser deposition (PLD) has been used to produce thin and dense CGO barrier layers (0.6-2 μm) but did not prevent the formation of SrZrO_3 at the YSZ/CGO interface despite the fabrication at low temperature [13,14,4]. It appears that there are fast diffusion pathways along the columnar grain boundaries due to the epitaxial growth of the barrier layer. Barrier layer annealing was conducted to reduce the number of grain boundaries but did not fully blocked the SrZrO_3 formation at the CGO/LSFC interface under polarization at high operation temperatures (900-1,000 °C) [4].

Optimization of the sintering temperature of a CGO barrier layer deposited at low temperature (600 °C) by PLD had been studied in a previous work of this group [15]. Sr and Zr inter-diffusion was limited applying a sintering temperature of 1,150 °C. This low sintering temperature also allowed minimizing the loss of Gd dopant from the CGO. Moreover, button cells with PLD barrier layer presented performances above 70 % compared to SoA cells made with screen-printed barrier layer. Those excellent results led to the fabrication of large-area cells of ~ 80 cm^2 with PLD CGO barrier layer and their electrochemical characterization in a stack together with SoA cells, tested in realistic conditions for long-term operation. After 6,500 h of real operation, the large-area cells with PLD barrier layer still presented higher performance and a degradation profile similar to the SoA large-area cells.

In this work, we made a post-operation analysis of the PLD barrier layer from the aforementioned large-area cells after extending the long-term test up to 14,000 h of operation. The effect of the long-term operation on the PLD barrier layer efficacy to limit the cation inter-diffusion at the LSCF/CGO/YSZ interfaces had been investigated by combining different analytical techniques such as Secondary Electron Microscopy, Electron Probe Micro Analysis with Wavelength Dispersive X-Ray (EPMA-WDX) and micro-Raman spectroscopy.

Experiments

Three anode-supported large-area cells were fabricated with standard techniques except for the barrier layer. Ni-YSZ cermet of 250 μm and YSZ electrolyte were manufactured by aqueous tape-casting and co-sintered above 1,400 °C. A dense CGO barrier layer of 2 μm

was deposited on top of the dense electrolyte by PLD technique at 600 °C, using a PVD5000 system (PVD Products). An annealing process was then realized at 1,150 °C. This temperature was optimized in a previous work in order to avoid the migration of Zr through the layer as well as limit the loss of Gd dopant and limit the diffusion of Sr during the cathode sintering step [15]. Finally, the LSCF-CGO composite cathode was deposited on top of the barrier layer by screen-printing and sintered, defining an active area of 80 cm².

Those large-area cells were electrochemically tested for 14,000 h in a stack made with 33 repeating units grouped in 11 clusters of cells with identical design and composition. Ferritic stainless steel cassette coated by ceramic protected coating to prevent Cr evaporation were used as interconnectors. A glass ceramic seal ensured the gas tightness between the anode and cathode chambers. Durability test was carried out by reproducing realistic operating conditions, which consisted in feeding the stack with natural gas partially steam reformed at a current density of 0.4 A·cm⁻², corresponding to 80 % of fuel utilization. Air was sent at the cathode. The operating temperature was set to 750 °C for 10,000 h (corresponding to 8,000 h of real operation) and then lowered to 700 °C until the end of the test. The operating temperature was self-sustained by the exothermic reactions occurring in the stack while the testing bench was not equipped with resistances to maintain a constant temperature. More details can be found in previous works [16-18].

Post-mortem analysis of the large-area cells and especially of the PLD barrier layer was performed by a complementary characterization of the cell cross-section by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Electron Probe Micro Analysis with Wavelength Dispersive X-Ray (EPMA-WDX) and Confocal Laser Raman Spectroscopy. Cross-section microstructure was examined by a Zeiss Auriga SEM. Elemental analysis was performed with a JEOL JXA-8230 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) equipped with an EPMA-WDX instead of an Energy Dispersive X-Ray analyzer due to an overlap of the emission lines for the L α -series in the characteristic X-ray spectra of Sr and Zr. The spatial distributions of Ce, Gd, Zr, Y and Sr elements were determined by EPMA-WDX line scans over YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO interfaces in order to evaluate their chemical reaction behavior. The spatial resolution of this equipment was equal to 0.5 μ m. Raman spectra were recorded on the LSCF/CGO/YSZ cross section using a high resolution, confocal Spectrometer HR800 (LabRAM Series, Horiba Jobin Yvon). An excitation line of 532 nm and a 100 \times objective were employed. The laser spot size was equal to 0.5 μ m. Spectra were recorded each 0.5 μ m along a line across the area YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO.

Results

Figure 1 presents the average voltage evolution with time of the cluster composed by three large-area cells with the PLD barrier layer, included in a stack operated with natural gas partially steam reformed at 0.4 A·cm⁻² and 80 % of fuel utilization. An initial voltage drop is observed during the first 500 h that is usually ascribed to particle coarsening and microstructure stabilization. The evolution of the voltage is then quite stable despite the thermal cycles operated for maintenance and/or improved thermal insulation (corresponding to the missing points). Before decreasing the temperature, after 10,200 h at 750 °C, the average degradation rate for the three large-area cells was equal to 0.47 %·kh⁻¹ from the beginning and 0.24 %·kh⁻¹ when removing the initial stabilization phase. Once the temperature was decreased to 700 °C, no more degradation was observed. It is worth mentioning that the clusters of SoA cells followed similar degradation profile even if they had lower performance (around 4 %) all over the test.

Figure 1. Average degradation curve of a three cells cluster, made with PLD CGO barrier layers, aged in a stack fuelled with natural gas partially steam reformed at the anode and air at the cathode.

Figure 2 shows the microstructure of the different layers of the large-area cells. One can see that after 14,000 h of operation, no obvious microstructural changes can be observed. There is still a good attachment of the cathode and the anode onto the barrier layer and the electrolyte respectively (**Figure 2a-c**). The dense barrier layer deposited by PLD is also perfectly attached to the electrolyte (**Figure 2a,b,d**). Moreover, the electrolyte does not present any visible cracks. However, it seems that some porosity of the electrolyte, usually considered as closed porosity, look bigger than before operation and are connected between each other. Bigger porosity is also observed at the interlayer anode/electrolyte that could result from a migration of the Ni as well as the Zr (**Figure 2a,c**). Finally, **Figure 2d** shows the presence of tiny porosity in some localized parts of the CGO barrier layer.

Figure 2. Cross-section SEM of the large-area cell with PLD CGO barrier layer aged for 14,000 h centered on a) the electrolyte, b) the interlayer electrolyte/PLD barrier layer/cathode, c) the interlayer anode/electrolyte and d) the PLD barrier layer.

Figure 3 presents the spatial distribution of the elements around the YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO area obtained by EPMA-WDX in order to verify if the PLD barrier layer played its role by blocking the inter-diffusion of Sr and Zr. The elements with high concentration (Ce, Zr) were plotted on one graph while the ones with lower concentration (Gd, Y and Sr) were gathered in a second one. The grey scale of the picture is also reported to identify better the transition between the different layers. The brightest part corresponds to the barrier layer while the darkest part can be attributed to a pore inside the cathode. First of all, the profile of Ce and Zr at the interlayer electrolyte/barrier layer shows an inter-diffusion of those species over 1 μm . The same profile is observed for the Y and Gd. This inter-diffusion was already observed on non-aged cells and ascribed to high temperature sintering steps of the cell manufacturing [15]. Then, a low and constant amount of Gd is detected along the electrolyte. A complementary study would be necessary to determine if it is a proper loss of dopant from the barrier layer and what would be the impact on its behavior. Moreover, a tiny bump is detected in the signal of Sr inside the PLD barrier layer close to the interface YSZ/CGO. As Zr is also detected at the same place, a small quantity of SrZrO_3 might have been formed there. A small amount of Zr was also detected close to the barrier layer/cathode interface, which can indicate the presence of the insulating phase SrZrO_3 .

Figure 3. WDX line scan at the interlayer YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO.

Raman analysis around the PLD barrier layer is presented **Figure 4** to assess the possible loss of dopant and the formation of insulating secondary phases. The most intense peak detected at $\sim 460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ inside the cathode can be assigned to the main peak of cubic CGO [19]. This peak shifts to $\sim 465 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ when reaching the barrier layer and the first microns of the electrolyte. This value can correspond to pure CeO_2 , which would evidence a loss of Gd as dopant of the CGO compound [6,20]. Regarding the results obtained by WDX, a complete loss of Gd does not seem to have happened, however the detection of Gd inside the electrolyte is consistent with the results obtained by Raman. Moreover, a peak at $\sim 555 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is detected together with a small peak at $\sim 695 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ inside the barrier layer and the electrolyte. The nature of the corresponding phase is not clear. It can be assigned to the insulating phase SrZrO_3 that presents characteristic peaks at those values but some other intense peaks at 160 and 413 cm^{-1} are missing. Further investigation is necessary to clearly evidence the formation of SrZrO_3 during the operation of those cells made with a dense barrier layer deposited by PLD.

Figure 4. Raman microprobe spectra measured on a cell cross-section, every 0.5 μm at the interlayer YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO.

Conclusions

In the present study, large-area cells with a CGO barrier layer deposited by PLD at low temperature and operated in a stack with realistic operating conditions were aged for 14,000 h in SOFC mode and then microstructurally characterized. Low degradation rates were observed all along the degradation profile, despite the decrease of the voltage due to a typical stabilization phase for the first 500 h and various thermal cycles due to maintenance and thermal optimization of the test bench. Post-mortem analysis, made by SEM, EPMA-WDX and Raman, were focused around the interlayer YSZ/CGO/LSCF-CGO. Main microstructure changes could not be evidenced by SEM. The barrier layer was perfectly attached to the electrolyte but small porosity was observed within localized spots of the layer. WDX results showed a small quantity of Sr at the electrolyte/barrier layer interface as well as some traces of Zr inside the oxygen electrode. Moreover, Gd was detected inside the electrolyte, which would correspond to a loss of dopant from the CGO layer. This result is aligned with the observation made by Raman spectroscopy where the main peak of CGO was shifted to higher wavelengths inside the barrier layer and first microns of the electrolyte, corresponding to a loss of dopant of the ceria. Regarding the inter-diffusion of Sr and Zr, two peaks appeared inside the YSZ and CGO that might be characteristic of the SrZrO_3 . However, part of the main peaks related to SrZrO_3 are missing, which makes necessary complementary analysis to confirm the formation of the insulating phases and the loss of Gd during the long-term operation.

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Keywords: EFCF2020, SOx

Session B15: Lifetime: Cells, components and interfaces

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